

MASS -TIME EQUIVALANCE AND ENERGY- TIME EQUIVALANCE

By

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Let us assume that the velocity of light is the maximum displacement in an unit time in universe and then the emission process of light should be the least minimum time taking action in universe. In that case being the least minimum time taking action, this duration also becomes the least rate of change in time or the duration to build the least wavelength that in turn becomes the least rate of change of time. There cannot be any further division of time in Universe.

i.e. using Plank – Einstein formula $\nu = E/h$

$$1/\nu = 1/E/h$$

$$\Delta t = h/E \text{ -----(1)}$$

becomes the absolute minimum action in Universe or the absolute minimum unit of time Δt in universe.

i.e $E \propto 1/\Delta t$ or -----(2)

$$E \propto 1/\lambda \text{ -----(3)}$$

then equating Einstein's energy mass equivalence gives us the mass – time equivalence we get

$$M \propto 1/\Delta t \text{ -----(4)}$$

Conclusion :

1. As we now know that the energy and mass are interchangeable with time through this equivalence formulas. Also time is a variable component.
2. At $\Delta t \rightarrow 0$, ie. at singularity mass becomes infinite as the situation constructed in big bang theory or as the mass increases, the time/space

shrinks as special theory of relativity suggests.

3. At $M \rightarrow 0$, Δt becomes infinite ie. Time stops when mass becomes zero.

Considering this is not $\Delta t \rightarrow 0$, the Universe is at static and at motion simultaneously or in other words for a light wave/quanta Universe is static and at motion simultaneously or cause and consequence will become complimentary.

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